

Effect of time of evaluation on alkali spreading values

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The gelatinization temperature of the endosperm starch, a test of rice cooking quality, is estimated by the extent of spreading and clearing of milled rice treated with a 1.7% solution of potassium hydroxide for 23 h at 30 °C. Grain with low gelatinization temperature dissolves completely; the endosperm of grain with intermediate gelatinization temperature spreads partially; rices with high gelatinization temperature are essentially unaffected.

We studied the effect of time of exposure in the alkali test using 41 Argentinian and United States varieties and lines of rices with alkali spreading values ranging from 2.62 to 7 in a random split-plot design with 3 replications. The alkali test was evaluated at 6, 12, 18, and 23 h following the original method. No significant difference in the varietal reaction was noted between alkali exposure at 18 and at 23 h (see table). □

Effect of soaking time on mean alkali spreading value of milled rice of 41 varieties.

Time (h)	Alkali spreading value
6	5.27 c
12	5.66 b
18	5.94 a
23	5.91 a
Tukey 5% 0.07	
Tukey 1% 0.1	

Mean values with the same letter are not significantly different from each other.

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High density grain index among primary and secondary tillers of short- and long-duration rices

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We conducted a multilocation field experiment using two short-duration and two long-duration varieties during 1985 wet season in a randomized block design with four replications. Test plots were fertilized 80-13-25 kg NPK/ha.

Tillers were sequentially labeled during crop growth and 50 panicles/replication were sampled at harvest. Density was measured by immersing the grain in a 1.20 specific gravity salt solution. The percentage of submerged high density grain from primary and secondary or tertiary tillers was recorded.

In early varieties, the high density grain index was higher for primary tillers than for secondary and tertiary tillers (see table). In late varieties, the indexes were equal. □

High density grain index (%) of primary and tertiary tillers of short and long-duration varieties. Hyderabad, India, 1985 kharif.

Variety	High density grain index				
	Hyderabad	Chinsurah	Kanpur	Kapurthala	Maruteru
Primary tillers					
Short duration					
Rasi	71.6	85.9	66.5	86.5	60.0
Ratna	55.7	72.8	71.2	79.0	29.0
Long duration					
Mahsuri	53.0	83.6	—	—	75.0
IET5656	61.8	81.2	—	—	90.0
CD (0.05)	5.2	2.4	ns	ns	4.1
CV (%)	4.3	1.5	9.8	5.1	3.3
Secondary and tertiary tillers					
Early					
Rasi	64.6	80.0	60.4	65.0	53.0
Ratna	50.4	71.5	38.0	75.0	23.0
Late					
Mahsuri	55.1	81.3	—	—	80.0
IETS 656	61.8	76.1	—	—	91.0
CD (0.05)	3.5	1.4	10.3	6.4	2.5
CV (%)	3.0	1.3	5.8	2.6	2.1

Genetic Evaluation and Utilization DISEASE RESISTANCE

Sugars and phenolic compounds in rice leaves in relation to varietal resistance to bacterial blight (BB) pathogen

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A few reports establish a relationship between phenolic and sugar constituents of rice leaves and resistance or susceptibility of a variety to BB caused

by *Xanthomonas campestris* pv. *oryzae* (Ishiyama) Dye.

Following standard procedures, we analyzed for total phenol, total sugar, and reducing sugars from alcoholic and aqueous extracts of apparently healthy rice leaves. The leaves were from plants that had been inoculated with the local BB isolate and showed resistant, moderately resistant, and highly susceptible disease reactions.

Highest total phenol, 278.26 mg/100 g of fresh leaves, was found in IR20, a resistant variety; the lowest, 100 mg/100

g of fresh leaves, in Anand, the highly susceptible check. This trend is reflected in reducing and total sugars as well.

The amount of phenol and sugars present in the leaves of resistant varieties varied considerably, but was always higher than that present in moderately susceptible Bhagalpuri, which in turn was higher than that present in highly susceptible Anand (see table).

These findings establish that higher amounts of phenols and sugars keep BB lesion size smaller by generating a resistant reaction to the BB pathogen. □

Total phenol and reducing and total sugar content in apparently healthy leaves from BB inoculated resistant (R), moderately resistant (MR), and highly susceptible (HS) rice varieties. Kumarganj, India.

Variety	Resistance level ^a	Reaction	Total phenol ^b (mg/100 g)	Reducing sugars ^b (mg/100 g)	Total sugars ^b (g/100 g)
IR20	1	R	278.26	114.40	1.1085
Anjani III	1	R	126.08	113.90	1.1080
Damodar	1	R	121.73	114.30	1.1059
Randhuri	1	R	117.39	114.00	1.1070
Getu	1	R	113.04	114.00	1.1060
Zeerabatti	1	R	113.04	113.90	1.1069
Bishunbhog	1	R	112.50	113.80	1.1058
Bhagalpuri	5	MR	104.34	113.70	1.1050
Anand	9	HS	100.00	113.50	1.1048

^a Standard evaluation system for rice (1980). ^b Fresh weight basis.

Field screening IRRI lines against tungro (RTV) disease in Lanrang

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To obtain sources of resistance to RTV for the breeding programs in Indonesia, we screened IRRI lines in the field in Lanrang substation during the 1986 wet monsoon season.

Lines tested were transplanted in 2 rows of 20 hills/row. Susceptible check variety TNI was transplanted between each two rows. All test lines and TNI were transplanted at 20- × 20cm spacing.

The trial was fertilized with urea and triple superphosphate at 90 kg N/ ha and 26 kg P/ ha. RTV symptoms were measured at 4, 6, and 8 wk after

Field screening of IRRI lines against tungro disease in Lanrang, Indonesia.

Line	SES rating		
	4 WT	6 WT	8 WT
IR1352	0	0	1
IR1354-21-2-3-3-2-2	0	0	1
IR31868-64-2-3-3-3	0	1	1
IR11288-B-B-60-1	0	1	3
IR14437-Kn-6-0-0-5-3	0	1	3
IR15864-430-3-1-2-3	0	1	3
IR19743-43-2-3-3	0	1	3
IR1975-5-2-3-1	0	1	3
IR21567-18-3	0	1	3
IR28224-3-2-3-2	0	1	3
IR28228-119-2-3-1-1	0	0	3
IR29692-99-3-2-1	1	1	3
IR31851-96-2-3-2-1	0	1	3
IR35546-2-1-3-2	0	1	3
IR37218-24-2-2	0	1	3
IR38784-137-2-6-6	0	0	3
IR4432-28-5-30Kr-b-Mr-3	0	1	3
IR4432-28-5-40Kr-b-Mr-9	1	3	3
IR18348-36-3-3	1	3	5
IR28128-45-3-3-2	0	3	5
IR29658-69-2-1	1	3	5
IR29925-22-3-3-3	1	3	5
IR31082-48-2-2	1	3	5
IR33450-25-2-1-1-2-2	1	3	5
IR35664-42-1-2-2-2-2	1	3	5

transplanting (WT) on the *Standard evaluation system for rice* (SES).

Of 400 lines tested, 18 were resistant and 7 moderately resistant (see table). □

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Manoharsali, neck blast-resistant variety

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During the 1986 Jul-Dec season, a severe neck and nodal blast (BI) incidence throughout Assam offered an opportunity to screen rice varieties against neck B1. Infection was assessed

Incidence of neck BI in 5 varieties in Assam, India.

Variety	Disease score ^a
Manoharsali	0
Kmj 1-17-2	0
Biraj	3
IET7251	9
Pusa 2-21	9

^a Standard evaluation system for rice.

on 20 randomly selected hills of 5 promising varieties grown in adjacent plots.

Manoharsali and Kmj 1-17-2 were totally free of neck BI (see table). Manoharsali also showed complete resistance to B1 in farmers' fields. This variety has been grown in Assam for 20 yr.

Kmj 1-17-2 is a derivative of the cross Manoharsali/IR8 and might have inherited resistance from Manoharsali.

Manoharsali also is tolerant of bacterial leaf blight and sheath blight and resistant to brown planthopper. It is susceptible to brown spot.